

Declaration of Commitment to Animal Welfare

We, the ASUBAGROIN Research Group attached to the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences of the University of Cauca, confirm our commitment to guaranteeing the well-being of all the organisms used in our research, including fish (red tilapia). Throughout our project, we have implemented a series of measures aimed at alleviating the suffering of these animals and ensuring that their management is carried out in an ethical and responsible manner.

To achieve this goal, we have adopted the following practices:

1. **Regulatory compliance:** We strictly adhere to Law 1774 of 2016 which establishes the "National Animal Protection Code" and recognizes animals as sentient beings, prohibiting mistreatment and establishing duties and rights in relation to their well-being. Likewise, Decree 84 of 1989 that regulates the protection of animals in the context of scientific research and establishes standards on the ownership of animals and their well-being, also, Resolution 1362 of 2018, issued by the Colombian Agricultural Institute (ICA), where the technical guidelines for the management and well-being of production animals are established.
2. **Training:** Researchers during the project were trained on humane fish handling, including proper handling, transportation and care techniques, as well as the importance of minimizing stress and pain in all procedures.
3. **Optimal Conditions:** the animals were placed in metabolic cages with adequate spaces simulating the natural conditions of the fish, providing an enriched environment that allows them to behave naturally, thus reducing the stress associated with captivity.
4. **Evaluation and Continuous Monitoring:** We have established evaluation protocols to identify any signs of suffering or discomfort in the animals. Our team of researchers was trained in animal behavior to carry out daily checks regarding water quality to maintain physicochemical parameters at acceptable levels for the species with the help of the NANOCOLOR colorimetry equipment. During the study, physical and chemical quality parameters of the body of water used were monitored. Physical characteristics mainly include temperature, pH and dissolved oxygen. Chemical characteristics include nitrite, nitrate, ammonium and phosphate parameters, which are preferably measured with rapid and sensitive kits. The water parameters for the management of individuals are described below (Table 1), to guarantee minimum stress and ensure that an optimal state of health is maintained.

After verifying the quality of the water, the metabolic cages were filled to the corresponding level. Subsequently, 23g sodium bisulfite was added to 200L, as a chlorine reducer, leaving it to act for 10 minutes. The water was then prepared at temperature conditions (approximately 26°C) and oxygen (5.7 mg/L and 90% saturation), which resemble the environment of origin of the animal, with the use of 150W brand submersible thermostats. RESUM RH9000 and two outlet aerators. Maintain stable oxygen levels and temperature during the duration of the test.

The food supplied must be consumed in its entirety, so that there are no excesses in the water that affect its physicochemical conditions.

Table 1. Water quality indices in Tilapia

Parameter	Allowed quantity
Oxygen	5.0 - 9.0 ppm
pH	6.0 -7.2
Temperature	25-32°C
Total Ammonium	< 0,1 mgL-1
Nitrate	1.5 - 2.0 ppm
Nitrite	< 0,75 ppm, tóxico > 5ppm
Phosphates	0.15 - 0.2 ppm

Fountain. Bautista, Ruiz, 2011; Saavedra, 2006

5. Feeding: the diets used in the research were formulated and balanced according to the nutritional requirements of the species under study, in this case the red tilapia (*Oreochromis sp.*) to reduce dietary stress.
6. Health Monitoring: We constantly monitor the health and well-being of the fish, implementing evaluation protocols that allow us to immediately detect and treat any signs of suffering or illness.
7. Anesthesia: In procedures that required intervention, we use approved organic anesthetics such as clove oil (*Syzygium aromaticum*) to minimize pain and stress.
8. Ethical Review: The research project was subjected to a rigorous ethical review by a specialized committee, which evaluated the proposed methods and their impact on fish welfare.

Through these efforts, we reaffirm our commitment to alleviating the suffering of fish used in our research. We will continue to look for ways to improve our practices and promote animal welfare in all our scientific activities.

Sincerely,

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